

COMPARISON OF FRACTURE RESISTANCE OF POSTERIOR TEETH RESTORED WITH DUAL CURE FLOWABLE COMPOSITE RESIN, ZIRCONOMER AND UNIVERSAL COMPOSITE RESTORATIVE MATERIAL: AN IN-VITRO STUDY

Dr. Vishal Mahajan¹, Dr. Priti Mahale², Dr. Rasik Bagde³, Dr. Pranali Satpute⁴

1(Professor and PG Guide, Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics, YCM Dental College)

2(Postgraduate Student, Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics, YCM Dental College)

3(Lecturer, Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics, YCM Dental College)

4(Lecturer, Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics, YCM Dental College)

Corresponding Author: Dr. Vishal mahajan¹

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Introduction:

Dental caries remains one of the most prevalent oral diseases worldwide and frequently results in extensive loss of tooth structure requiring restorative treatment.¹ Restoration of posterior teeth with extensive mesio-occluso-distal (MOD) cavity preparations presents a significant challenge in restorative dentistry because such preparations considerably weaken the remaining tooth structure.^{2,3}

The fracture resistance of a tooth is greatly influenced by the amount of remaining sound tooth structure. Loss of marginal ridges and supporting dentin during cavity preparation results in increased cuspal deflection, reduced stiffness, and greater susceptibility to fracture under occlusal loading.^{3,4} Previous studies have shown that MOD cavity preparations significantly reduce the fracture strength and rigidity of posterior teeth.^{3,4}

Posterior teeth are continuously subjected to compressive, tensile, shear, and torsional forces during mastication. Therefore, restorative materials used in stress-bearing posterior regions should possess adequate mechanical properties, fracture toughness, and resistance to functional loading.^{2,5}

Premolars are considered more susceptible to fracture because of their anatomical morphology and steep cuspal inclinations. Their position in the dental arch subjects them to considerable occlusal stresses during mastication, making them suitable for in vitro fracture resistance studies.^{5,6}

With advancements in restorative dentistry, several restorative materials have been developed to improve the mechanical performance and longevity of posterior restorations. Composite restorative materials are widely used because of their esthetic properties, adhesive bonding mechanism, and favorable mechanical characteristics.⁷ Adhesive restorations help reinforce weakened tooth structure by distributing occlusal stresses more evenly across the tooth-restoration interface.⁸

Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow is a dual-cure flowable composite restorative material designed for core build-up procedures and restorative applications requiring improved cavity adaptation and handling characteristics.⁹ Flowable composites demonstrate superior adaptability because of their low viscosity; however, their lower filler content may adversely affect fracture resistance.¹⁰

Zirconomer is a zirconia reinforced glass ionomer restorative material developed to overcome the limitations associated with conventional glass ionomer cements.¹¹ Incorporation of zirconia particles enhances the compressive strength, fracture toughness, and wear resistance of the material.^{11,12} In addition, Zirconomer exhibits fluoride release and chemical adhesion to tooth structure, which may contribute to improved clinical performance.¹³

Kulzer Charisma Universal Composite is a micro-hybrid composite restorative material with favorable esthetic and mechanical properties suitable for posterior restorations.^{7,8} Composite restorations provide improved reinforcement to weakened teeth because of adhesive bonding and filler reinforced resin matrix.⁸

Although several studies have evaluated fracture resistance of different restorative materials, limited literature is available comparing dual-cure flowable composite resin, zirconia reinforced glass ionomer cement, and universal composite restorative material under standardized conditions.^{1,5} Therefore, the present in vitro study was conducted to assess and compare the fracture resistance of posterior teeth restored with Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow, Zirconomer, and Kulzer Charisma Universal Composite restorative material.

Aims And Objectives:

AIM–To access and compare fracture resistance of teeth restored with Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow, Zirconomer and Kulzer Charisma Universal Composite.

OBJECTIVES–

- 1.To assess the fracture resistance of teeth with class II MOD cavity prepared and unrestored.
2. To assess the fracture resistance of tooth restored with Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow.
3. To assess the fracture resistance of tooth restored with Zirconomer .
4. To assess the fracture resistance of tooth restored with Universal Composite restorative material (Kulzer Charisma).

Materials and Methodology:

The present in vitro comparative experimental study was conducted to evaluate and compare the fracture resistance of posterior teeth restored with different restorative materials. A total of thirty-six freshly extracted human maxillary premolars extracted for orthodontic purposes were selected for the study. Teeth included in the study were free from caries, restorations, cracks, fractures, abrasion, attrition, developmental defects, and endodontic treatment. Immediately after extraction, all teeth were cleaned thoroughly to remove debris and soft tissue remnants and were stored in normal saline at room temperature to prevent dehydration and preserve the physical properties of the tooth structure.

The selected samples were randomly divided into four groups consisting of nine specimens each. Group I consisted of teeth with standardized Class II mesio-occluso-distal (MOD) cavity preparation left unrestored and served as the control group. Group II consisted of teeth restored with Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow dual-cure flowable composite restorative material. Group III consisted of teeth restored with Zirconomer restorative material (Shofu Inc.), whereas Group IV consisted of teeth restored with Kulzer Charisma Universal Composite restorative material.

Standardized Class II MOD cavity preparations were performed in all specimens using a high-speed airtor handpiece with continuous water coolant and tungsten carbide burs. The cavity dimensions were standardized for all teeth to maintain uniformity among the samples. The preparation involved removal of both proximal marginal ridges along with the occlusal portion, thereby simulating extensive posterior tooth destruction. All internal line angles were rounded to minimize stress concentration during loading procedures.

For Group II specimens, the prepared cavity surfaces were etched with 37% phosphoric acid etchant, rinsed thoroughly with water, and gently air dried. Bonding agent was then applied according to the manufacturer's instructions and light cured. Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow dual-cure flowable composite restorative material was placed incrementally into the prepared cavity and polymerized using an LED light curing unit.

For Group III, the prepared cavities were restored using Zirconomer restorative material according to the manufacturer's recommendations. The material was manipulated according to the specified powder-liquid ratio and condensed into the prepared cavities. Excess restorative material was removed and finishing procedures were carried out after the initial setting reaction.

For Group IV specimens, the cavity surfaces were etched followed by application of bonding agent and light curing. Kulzer Charisma Universal Composite restorative material was then placed incrementally into the prepared cavity, and each increment was individually light cured to ensure adequate polymerization and adaptation.

Following restoration, all specimens were vertically embedded in self-cure acrylic resin blocks up to the cemento-enamel junction while maintaining the long axis of the tooth

perpendicular to the base. The mounted samples were then subjected to fracture resistance testing using a universal testing machine. A compressive load was applied vertically along the long axis of the tooth using a steel indenter until fracture occurred. The maximum load required to fracture each specimen was recorded in Newtons (N).

Statistical Analysis:

The obtained data were tabulated and statistically analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 23.0. The level of statistical significance was kept at 5% ($p < 0.05$). Data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk normality test. Comparison of fracture resistance among the four groups was performed using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) followed by post hoc pairwise comparison analysis.

Results:

The fracture resistance values obtained from all experimental groups were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS software version 23.0. Comparison of fracture resistance among the four groups was performed using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test followed by post hoc pairwise comparison analysis. The level of statistical significance was kept at $p < 0.05$.

The mean fracture resistance values recorded for Group I (Unrestored teeth), Group II (Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow), Group III (Zirconomer), and Group IV (Kulzer Charisma Universal Composite) were 1985.00 N, 734.67 N, 1227.78 N, and 1090.89 N respectively. The highest fracture resistance was observed in unrestored teeth followed by Zirconomer, Kulzer Charisma Composite, and Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow restorative material.

One-way ANOVA revealed a statistically highly significant difference in fracture resistance among all four groups with an F-value of 912.92 and p-value < 0.001 .

Group	Mean FR	SD	F-value	p-value
Unrestored teeth	1985.00	75.76	912.92	$< 0.001^*$

Zirconomer	1227.78	36.63		
Charisma Composite	1090.89	45.18		
Dentsply Sirona Core X Flow	734.67	42.48		

F-value = 912.92

p-value < 0.001 (Highly Significant)

Pairwise comparison between the groups also demonstrated statistically significant differences among all experimental groups. The mean difference between unrestored teeth and Zirconomer was found to be 757.22 N, between unrestored teeth and Kulzer Charisma Composite was 894.11 N, and between unrestored teeth and Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow was 1250.33 N. Similarly, statistically significant differences were observed between Zirconomer and Kulzer Charisma Composite, Zirconomer and Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow, and Kulzer Charisma Composite and Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow groups with p-value <0.001.

Group	Mean difference	p-value
Unrestored teeth vs Zirconomer	757.22	<0.001*
Unrestored teeth vs Charisma Composite	894.11	<0.001*
Unrestored teeth vs Dentsply Sirona Core X Flow	1250.33	<0.001*
Zirconomer vs Charisma Composite	136.89	<0.001*
Zirconomer vs Dentsply Sirona Core X Flow	493.11	<0.001*
Charisma Composite vs Dentsply Sirona Core X Flow	356.22	<0.001*

Discussion

Fracture resistance is considered one of the most important mechanical properties of restorative materials used in posterior teeth because these teeth are continuously subjected to complex occlusal forces during mastication.^{2,5} Extensive mesio-occluso-distal (MOD) cavity preparations considerably weaken the remaining tooth structure by causing loss of marginal ridges and supporting dentin, thereby increasing cuspal deflection and susceptibility to fracture under functional loading.^{3,4} Therefore, restorative materials used in posterior stress-bearing regions should possess adequate mechanical strength and fracture toughness to withstand functional stresses.²

In the present study, intact unrestored teeth exhibited the highest fracture resistance among all groups. This finding may be attributed to preservation of natural tooth structure and maintenance of the biomechanical integrity of enamel and dentin.^{3,4} The presence of intact marginal ridges contributes significantly to tooth rigidity and resistance against fracture.³ Mondelli et al. demonstrated that fracture strength decreases progressively with increasing removal of tooth structure, especially in extensive MOD cavity preparations.³ Similarly, Reeh et al. reported that MOD cavity preparation significantly reduces cuspal stiffness and structural rigidity of posterior teeth.⁴

Maxillary premolars were selected for the present study because they are anatomically more susceptible to fracture due to their steep cuspal inclinations and unfavorable crown morphology.^{5,6} During mastication, premolars are exposed to considerable compressive and

shear stresses, making them suitable candidates for evaluating fracture resistance of restorative materials.⁵

Among the restorative materials evaluated, Zirconomer demonstrated the highest fracture resistance. Zirconomer is a zirconia reinforced glass ionomer restorative material developed to improve the mechanical properties of conventional glass ionomer cements.¹¹ The superior fracture resistance observed in the present study may be attributed to the incorporation of zirconia particles within the restorative matrix. Zirconia possesses excellent mechanical properties such as high compressive strength, fracture toughness, wear resistance, and resistance to crack propagation.^{11,12}

The improved performance of Zirconomer may also be related to the homogeneous distribution of zirconia fillers, which enhances structural integrity and increases resistance to occlusal loading.¹² Chalissery et al. reported that zirconia reinforced glass ionomer cements exhibited enhanced mechanical properties and improved load-bearing capacity because of the reinforcing effect of zirconia fillers.¹² Similarly, Kamath and Salam observed greater fracture resistance in premolars restored with Zirconomer due to the transformation toughening mechanism of zirconia particles, which helps resist crack propagation.¹⁴

Another important factor contributing to the favorable performance of Zirconomer is its chemical adhesion to tooth structure along with fluoride releasing ability.^{11,13} Chemical bonding between the restorative material and tooth structure may improve stress distribution across the tooth-restoration interface and reduce stress concentration during functional loading.¹³ Naz et al. reported that Zirconomer demonstrated superior compressive strength and favorable mechanical performance because of its reinforced composition and improved physicochemical properties.¹³

Kulzer Charisma Universal Composite demonstrated moderate fracture resistance values in the present study. Composite restorative materials are widely used in posterior restorations because of their favorable esthetic properties, adhesive bonding mechanism, and satisfactory mechanical strength.⁷ The fracture resistance exhibited by Kulzer Charisma Composite may be attributed to the presence of micro-hybrid filler particles and resin matrix, which together improve mechanical strength and wear resistance.^{7,10}

Composite restorative materials reinforce weakened tooth structure through micromechanical bonding to enamel and dentin.⁸ Adhesive bonding helps distribute functional stresses more evenly throughout the restored tooth, thereby reducing cuspal deflection and minimizing stress concentration.⁸ Hamouda and Shehata reported that posterior teeth restored with composite materials demonstrated improved reinforcement because of adhesive bonding and favorable mechanical properties of resin composites.⁸

Despite their favorable properties, composite restorative materials may still be affected by polymerization shrinkage and shrinkage stress generated during curing.⁷ Polymerization shrinkage can induce stresses at the tooth-restoration interface, potentially compromising marginal adaptation and long-term fracture resistance.⁷ Ferracane stated that although resin composites possess excellent esthetic and mechanical characteristics, polymerization

shrinkage remains one of the major disadvantages associated with resin-based restorative materials.⁷

In the present study, Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow demonstrated the lowest fracture resistance among the restorative materials tested. Core-X Flow is a dual-cure flowable composite restorative material commonly used for core build-up procedures because of its low viscosity, easy handling, and adaptability to cavity walls.⁹ However, the lower fracture resistance observed in this study may be attributed to its lower filler content and flowable consistency.¹⁰

Flowable composites generally possess lower modulus of elasticity and lower fracture toughness compared to heavily filled restorative composites.¹⁰ Although their low viscosity allows better adaptation to cavity walls, the reduced filler loading may compromise their resistance to high compressive forces. Wang et al. reported that filler concentration plays an important role in determining the mechanical properties and fracture resistance of restorative materials.¹⁰

The findings of the present study are in accordance with previous investigations evaluating fracture resistance of restorative materials in posterior teeth. Swathi et al. compared fracture resistance of MOD cavities restored with composite resin, resin modified glass ionomer cement, and Zirconomer and concluded that zirconia reinforced restorative materials demonstrated superior fracture resistance compared to conventional restorative materials.¹ Similarly, Khatib et al. observed statistically significant differences in fracture resistance among various restorative materials used in premolar restorations.⁵

The present study also demonstrated that all restored groups exhibited lower fracture resistance compared to intact unrestored teeth. This finding emphasizes the importance of conservative cavity preparation and preservation of natural tooth structure whenever possible.^{3,4} Preservation of enamel and dentin contributes significantly to the structural integrity and longevity of teeth.³

The methodology used in the present study involved the use of a universal testing machine to apply compressive loading until fracture occurred. Universal testing machines are commonly used in in vitro studies because they provide standardized and reproducible loading conditions.² However, laboratory conditions cannot completely replicate the complex oral environment where restorations are subjected to dynamic and multidirectional forces, thermal changes, saliva, cyclic fatigue, and parafunctional habits.⁸

The present study had certain limitations. The study was conducted under in vitro conditions, which do not completely simulate clinical situations. The sample size was relatively limited, and only maxillary premolars were included in the study. In addition, long-term fatigue behavior and clinical performance of the restorative materials could not be evaluated. Therefore, further long-term clinical studies with larger sample sizes and thermocycling protocols are recommended to validate the findings of the present investigation.^{1,8}

Conclusion:

Within the limitations of the present in vitro study, it can be concluded that the type of restorative material significantly influences the fracture resistance of posterior teeth restored with extensive mesio-occluso-distal (MOD) cavity preparations. Intact unrestored teeth demonstrated the highest fracture resistance among all groups evaluated.

Among the restorative materials tested, Zirconomer exhibited the highest fracture resistance, indicating its superior ability to reinforce weakened posterior teeth and withstand occlusal loading. Kulzer Charisma Universal Composite demonstrated moderate fracture resistance with satisfactory reinforcing ability, whereas Dentsply Sirona Core-X Flow exhibited the lowest fracture resistance among the restorative materials evaluated.

Based on the findings of the present study, Zirconomer may be considered a suitable restorative material for posterior stress-bearing areas where enhanced fracture resistance is required. However, further long-term clinical studies and in vivo investigations are recommended to validate the clinical performance and longevity of these restorative materials under functional oral conditions.

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